

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Dimethyl and Diphenyl Sulphoxides by MnO_4^- in Acid Medium

S. S. MOHANTY and P. MOHANTY*

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004

Manuscript received 15 February 1995, revised 24 April 1996, accepted 16 July 1997

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of DMSO (dimethyl sulphoxide) and DPhSO (diphenyl sulphoxide) with MnO_4^- have been studied in aqueous acetic acid (1.75 mol dm^{-3}) in $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$, using a stopped flow spectrophotometer in the temperature range 20 ± 0.1 to $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The main products of the reactions are the corresponding sulphones. The reaction is first order each in [substrate] and $[MnO_4^-]$ and the rate increases with the increase in substrate concentration. The redox reaction corresponds to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{OX}} K [\text{R}_2\text{SO}][\text{MnO}_4^-]_T [\text{H}^+] / (1 + K[\text{H}^+])$$

The values of the activation parameters have been evaluated.

Oxidation of organic compounds by MnO_4^- has been extensively studied both in acid and neutral medium¹ and oxidation of DMSO has been studied using various oxidants in different media²⁻⁴. Ag^I and Cu^{II} catalysed $S_2O_8^{2-}$ oxidation of DMSO⁵ has also been carried out, but no attempt has been made to study MnO_4^- oxidation of DMSO and DPhSO in acid medium.

Here we report the MnO_4^- oxidation of DMSO and DPhSO in the presence of $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in acetic acid + water medium.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) increase with the increase in [substrate] for both the reactants (Table 1). $10^2 k_{\text{obs}}$ at 35° changed from $2.5 \pm 0.15 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $28.5 \pm 0.35 \text{ s}^{-1}$ when $10^2 [\text{DPhSO}]$ changed from 0.06 to 0.6 mol dm^{-3} , similarly $10^2 k_{\text{obs}}$ changed from $8.2 \pm 0.6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $84.5 \pm 4.1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ when $10^2 [\text{DMSO}]$ changed from 0.06 to 0.6 mol dm^{-3} . At a fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ of 2.0 mol dm^{-3} , the k_{obs} vs $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T$ plot is linear passing through origin. However, the second order rate constants $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{substrate}]$ is invariant at a given temperature (Table 1). Thus the rate is first order in both $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and [substrate]. In a strongly acidic medium, MnO_4^- is protonated to produce $HMnO_4$ ^{6,7}. The following equilibrium exists between MnO_4^- and $HMnO_4$ in acidic medium,

$HMnO_4$ participates in the redox reaction. At a fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ the probable mechanism may be delineated as in Scheme 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] ON THE OXIDATION REACTION

Temp. = 35° , $[MnO_4^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $(\text{HAc}) = 1.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[H^+] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$10^2 [\text{R}_2\text{SO}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	
	DMSO	DPhSO
0.06	8.2 ± 0.6	2.5 ± 0.15
0.08	11.0 ± 1.0	3.5 ± 0.52
0.10	14.2 ± 1.2	4.8 ± 0.18
0.12	17.3 ± 1.3	6.2 ± 0.21
0.14	19.1 ± 0.9	6.8 ± 0.16
0.18	21.3 ± 1.7	7.7 ± 0.15
0.20	27.5 ± 1.9	9.4 ± 0.27
0.22	30.0 ± 2.0	10.5 ± 0.12
0.25	33.2 ± 1.5	12.3 ± 0.60
0.26	36.0 ± 3.0	12.6 ± 0.50
0.28	38.5 ± 2.6	13.0 ± 0.60
0.30	42.5 ± 0.7	13.8 ± 0.00
0.32	44.5 ± 0.3	15.1 ± 0.23
0.35	49.8 ± 2.0	15.5 ± 0.00
0.38	55.0 ± 2.0	15.9 ± 0.00
0.40	57.2 ± 3.5	18.1 ± 0.18
0.42	59.5 ± 4.0	20.2 ± 0.54
0.45	62.5 ± 0.3	21.2 ± 0.42
0.48	67.4 ± 3.0	22.1 ± 0.75
0.50	70.1 ± 2.5	22.5 ± 0.50
0.52	73.5 ± 3.0	24.5 ± 0.24
0.54	76.3 ± 3.2	25.4 ± 0.54
0.56	79.0 ± 4.0	26.6 ± 0.26
0.58	82.3 ± 3.2	27.5 ± 0.30
0.60	84.5 ± 4.1	28.5 ± 0.35

$$k_2 = 139.2 \pm 5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$$

$$k_2 = 46.8 \pm 2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$$

k_2 and k_2' are the average second order rate constants for the MnO_4^- oxidation reaction of DMSO and DPhSO at 35°

Thus the redox reaction corresponds to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_{\text{OX}}K[\text{R}_2\text{SO}][\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}[\text{H}^+]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (1)$$

under the experimental condition $K[\text{H}^+] \ll 1$ ($\text{p}K$ of HMnO_4 at $25^\circ = -2.25$)⁶ and equation (1) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{OX}}K[\text{R}_2\text{SO}][\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}[\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

At constant $[\text{H}^+]$, $K[\text{H}^+]$ is constant at a given temperature.

If $k'_1 = k_{\text{OX}}K[\text{H}^+]$, equation (2) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k'_1[\text{R}_2\text{SO}][\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}} \quad (3)$$

Since $\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}}$, equation (3) reduces to

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k'_1[\text{R}_2\text{SO}] \quad (4)$$

The k_{obs} vs [substrate] plot (figure not shown) which is linear and passing through origin, supports the above mechanism. The k_{obs} values for DMSO are found to be greater than that of DPhSO at any given temperature. The greater reactivity of DMSO in comparison to DPhSO can be explained in the following manner. The methyl groups of DMSO have strong +I effect and they increase electron density at the sulphur atom but the phenyl groups of DPhSO exert -I effect and they reduce the electron density at the sulphur atom of the $>\text{S}=\text{O}$ group, making DPhSO a poorer electron donor in comparison to DMSO. Permanganic acid produced by the reaction of MnO_4^- with H^+ oxidises dimethyl and diphenyl sulphoxides to the corresponding sulphones. HMnO_3 evolved in the rate-determining step⁸ produced MnO_4^- and Mn^{2+} and water. The $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values for the redox reactions, calculated using Eyring equation are given in Table 2. Activation free energy change is more favourable for the oxidation of DMSO in comparison to DPhSO. The large negative activation entropy of DPhSO oxidation in comparison to DMSO oxidation reaction can be ascribed to highly ordered activated state for DPhSO in comparison to DMSO.

Experimental

A stock solution of potassium permanganate was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised. Dimethyl sulphoxide (AnalaR) was distilled over CaO under reduced pressure and diphenyl sulphoxide recrystallised before use and its purity checked by comparing the m.p. with standard value. Acetic acid was used as a solvent to dissolve the substrate. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Rate measurement : The experiment was carried out in the temperature range 20 ± 0.1 to $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ varying the concentration of the substrates. The rate measurements were made under pseudo-first order condition using $10^2 [\text{R}_2\text{SO}] = 0.06\text{--}0.6$ and $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{T}} = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The redox reaction was followed in a HI-TECH (UK) SF 51 stopped flow spectrophotometer automated by an Apple II GS computer. The rate constant for any run was taken to be the average from five determinations and its error quoted in the standard deviation. The molar extinction coefficient of MnO_4^- used was ($\epsilon_{530} = 900 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The redox reaction was followed at 520 nm.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : After completion of the reaction, the product was separated and treated with crushed ice to get the sulphones which was washed with distilled water and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$). The crystals and authentic samples of dimethyl sulphones were applied on the same plate and developed. The spots were identified by exposure to iodine and solvent system used was benzene-ethanol (4 : 1, v/v) mixture. The R_f value of the product of oxidation agreed with the authentic sample. The runs undertaken in the presence of excess substrate in 1.75 mol dm^{-3} acetic acid and KMnO_4 in $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at 35° indicates that 5 moles of the substrate reacts with 2 moles of MnO_4^- . The following reaction takes place between the sulphoxides and MnO_4^- in acid medium,

where, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ and C_6H_5 for DMSO and DPhSO.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE OXIDATION OF DMSO AND DPhSO BY MnO_4^- IN ACID MEDIUM

Substrate		Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)					$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		20	25	30	35	40		
DMSO ^a ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)			78.7 ± 2	100.9 ± 3	140.6 ± 5	180 ± 5	41 ± 2	-72 ± 6
DPhSO ^a ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)		24.1 ± 2	30.3 ± 0.4	38.8 ± 0.2	45.3 ± 0.6		28 ± 4	-121.0 ± 12
DPhSO ^b							51.6	-143.0
DPhSO ^c							51.6	-140.0

^aPresent work. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 3

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. C. Dash and Dr. D. Bhatta for their help and valuable suggestions.

References

1. P. S. R. MURTY and P. S. MOHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 1294; P. S. R. MURTY and S. N. SAHU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1154; C. F. CULLIS and J. W. LADBURY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 555; R. CURCI and G. MODENA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1963, **14**, 1749.
2. S. M. BEHERA, D. BHATTA and S. R. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 778.
3. S. M. BEHERA, D. BHATTA and S. R. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 776.
4. A. K. ROY, H. K. PRATHARI and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 4; Y. OGATA and K. TANAKA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1981, **59**, 718; N. G. DEVI and V. MAHADEVAN, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 797; A. GIBSON and B. G. COX, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 1355; S. C. PADHI and P. S. R. MURTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1097.
5. A. S. REDDY and J. N. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 608.
6. N. BAILEY and A. CARRINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 290.
7. K. K. BANERJI and P. NATH, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, **42**, 2038.
8. P. R. RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 502.